

1 **Neuroactive molecule engagement during TNBC resistance.**

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7 Peptide *PYY2* was among those most abundantly increased during resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro*.
8 We also found adrenoceptor *ADRA1D* and adrenomedullin *ADM2* activation during resistance to
9 chemotherapy.

10 Citations

11 1. Couzens, M., Liu, M., Tüchler, C., Kofler, B., Nessler-Menardi, C., Parker, R.M., Klocker, H. and
12 Herzog, H., 2000. Peptide YY-2 (PYY2) and pancreatic polypeptide-2 (PPY2): species-specific evolution of
13 novel members of the neuropeptide Y gene family. *Genomics*, 64(3), pp.318-323.